

Ways of improvement of defence planning mechanism in the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine

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Abstract

The article focuses on generalizing the requirements of the current legislation, other normative legal acts, own theoretical studies and assessing the effectiveness of defense and budget planning systems in Ukraine.

At present, defense reform is based on the principles and principles governing the NATO member states, which in turn requires a revision of the current system and the introduction of new approaches and mechanisms in the defense and budget planning system.

The goal of this article is revealing defence planning mechanism improvement ways in the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine.

Key words: defense reform, defense and budget planning, budget.

Introduction

The planning in the national security sphere – is a function of government administration for determination of priorities, objectives and activities for ensuring the national security of Ukraine, balanced development of security and defence sector components on the basis of situation security assessment and in view of financial-economic state abilities.

Defence planning sphere is very important not only for Ukraine, but also for any state, which strives to have powerful army, high

standards

and reliable protection level of the territorial integrity and state sovereignty. It would make sense to accentuate, among important scientific objectives, the nature revealing of defence and strategic planning, organization of which is regulated by standard legal acts; providing of main directions characteristics of reformation of defence sphere legislation and proposal of its improvement ways to achieve the goals mentioned above.

Material and methods

The designated topic has direct connection with important scientific and practical objectives of a number of all-combined arms and legal disciplines, as well as political sciences. The national security of Ukraine sphere has always been very interesting topic for scientists, interested in the military problematic. These issues became the subject of scientific interest

of such Ukrainian researchers, as I. Romanchenko, V Bohdanovych, M. Dieniezhkin, P. Krykun, V. Pavlenko.

During the research, the following methods were used: method of critical analysis of documents, “case study” method, and logical-intuitive method.

Results and discussion

The important part of the national security is defence planning as an integral part of the national strategic planning system, which is carried out in order to ensure the state defence potential via determination of priorities and defence forces development directions, their capabilities, armament and materiel, infrastructure, troops (forces) training, and development of respective concepts, programs and plans in the context of real and potential threats in the military sphere and financial-economic abilities of the state.

Defence planning directly associated with national development strategic planning.

The scientists defined the term “strategy” in different ways:

1. art of political struggle managing;
2. goals with an order of priorities for their implementation, as well as art of situation prediction ability;
3. system of decisions, directed to goals achievement.

Herewith, the national security strategy can be described as practical actions program for ensuring the national security, which is coordinated with goals, objectives, circumstances, means and time. The Law of Ukraine “On defence planning organization” (repealed in 2018) contained similar definition of a term “National security strategy of Ukraine” – it was a long-term practical actions complex program concerning the ensuring of vital interests protection of person, community and state from external and internal threats coordinated with goal, objectives, circumstances, and means. National security strategy of Ukraine is a background for complex planning of governmental bodies activity in the spheres of defence and national security.

According to the Law of Ukraine “On national security of Ukraine”, the defence planning – is an integral part of a state strategic planning system, which is carried out in order to ensure the state defence potential via determination of priorities and defence forces development directions, their capabilities, armament and materiel, infrastructure, troops (forces) training,

and development of respective concepts, programs and plans in the context of real and potential threats in the military sphere and financial-economic abilities of the state;

In accordance with the Order of the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine from 22 December, 2020, №484 “About approval the order of organization and implementation defence planning in the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine and the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other components of the defense forces” chiefs of military command and control bodies, during the planning of Armed Forces of Ukraine development and support activities for the period up to 2021 have to use the following as a guidance:

- main provisions of the Strategic Defence Bulletin of Ukraine;
- State Program for the Development of Armed Forces of Ukraine;
- State target defence program for the armament and materiel development;
- development programs of troops (forces) branches and separate services of Armed Forces of Ukraine;
- military-political directions concerning military policy formation and implementation in the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine and the Armed Forces of Ukraine for the period up to 2021;
- results of the activities accomplishment of the Armed Forces of Ukraine development and support plan on every year;
- assignment of the responsible (person\body) for execution of strategic (operational) development goals (objectives);
- assignment of the development and budget programs (subprograms) directions due to the Armed Forces of Ukraine activity segments.

Moreover, chiefs of military command and control bodies have to take into considerations the provisions of:

- Military Standard “Defence planning. Development and support plan of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Procedure of development, execution and reporting” VST 01.040.001-2013 (01) (as amended);

- Military Standard “Defence planning. Oriented support and development plan of the Armed Forces of Ukraine for the next year and two further years. Procedure of development and employment” VST 01.040.002-2014 (01).

Therefore, in the context of defence planning, the Strategy – is a behavior model, directed to the assigned goals achievement, a set of rules for search and exploitation of opportunities. The Strategic plan – is a sequence of specific steps and actions, integrated into space and time, which provokes transformation of actual situation to the desirable.

Defence planning system in Ukraine – is an integral part of the state defence planning systems, state resources management in the sphere of defence and budget planning. On principal, the defence planning system in Ukraine is similar to the respective procedures, adopted in NATO and EU that maximally simplify process of its adaptation to the collective planning requirements in the future. One of the key parts of national defence planning system is NATO process of planning and forces assessment, which is used by Ukraine for the Armed Forces of Ukraine reformation and development tasks implementation, along with the NATO-Ukraine Joint Working Group recommendations on defence reform.

Defence planning subjects in the Armed Forces are structural units of the Ministry of Defence and the General Staff of the Armed Forces of Ukraine by the directions of their responsibilities. Objects of the defence planning are: the Armed Forces of Ukraine branches and formations, military units, military educational institutions, departments and organizations, which are not belong to the Armed Forces of Ukraine branches.

Strategic defensive review is a start point of this process. The strategic defensive review fullness, quality of prepared, by its results, reporting informational-analytical materials and precise determination of development perspectives of planning objects create the foundation for effective defence planning.

Projection indexes of spending of State budget of Ukraine for the defence needs in long-term and mid-term perspectives are an

important basis for defence planning, which admits to achieve a balance between defence reform ambitious goals and resource capabilities. They allow to conduct financial-economic calculations for defence forces development activities and estimate risks in defence planning results achieving.

Defence planning based on capabilities is one of the planning methods, peculiarity of which is defence forces capabilities development for military and non-military effective threats and risks countering considering the most probable scenarios of crisis situations development in long-term perspectives, usually for 10-15 years. This defence planning method is fundamental for NATO member-states.

Defence planning based on capabilities makes provision for the functional analysis carrying out. Functions and objectives, which have to be accomplished during prospective operations, are being transformed in capabilities demand, whereby their formation, support and development are being planned. Defence planning based on capabilities makes provision for formation, development and support for optimal required capabilities within available resources.

Complex combination of defence planning capabilities, mechanisms and array of tools based on capabilities and threats, is the most acceptable for Ukraine under the current conditions with respect to NATO defence planning principles and standards. Following specific planning methods are used with them: planning based on resources, step-by-step planning and planning based on scenarios.

At present, two parallel systems are employed in Ukraine during planning and financing of the Armed Forces of Ukraine development process. From the one side defence planning, in the framework of which the activities planning and development program management are being occurred and the Armed Forces of Ukraine budgeting or financing on the other side. Currently, the attempts to integrate these two systems are made, but there are some disadvantages in the consistency of criteria. Improvement of defence planning system and financing, in particular financial planning

(budget planning), takes on special importance under the conditions of the Joint Forces Operation conducting in the east of Ukraine and underfunding of National Defence requirements.

Defence planning processes have cyclic nature:

The long-term cycle of the defence planning is carried out by the results of defence inspection and completed by the adoption of reported informational-analytical materials and approving of strategic long-term defence planning documents.

The five-year cycle of defence planning is carried out at least than one time per five years. In a process of five-year cycle, the mid-term defence planning of defence forces development and appropriate programmed and planned documents adoption are carried out.

The annual cycle of the defence planning is carried in a year, which is precedes the year, when respective events are planned. In a process of this cycle the short-term planning is carried out, and its events are synchronized with events of budget planning in the state.

One of the main tasks of defence planning is a rational distribution and effective using of limited financial resources on the needs of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. The annual specification is being carried out during the short-term defence planning, which is attached to the budgetary process in Ukraine. The results of performing short-term planning procedure are the budget request, the finance plan of the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine and the specified plan of support and development of the Armed Forces of Ukraine.

During the defence planning implementation (long-, mid-, or short-term) the Armed Forces development is being planned according to specified missions execution. In other words, firstly the level of the military threats and the nature of modern military conflicts and trends of the armed combat development are estimated, the list of cases of the Armed Forces employment is determined, their missions are formed and the procedure of their execution is modulated, the necessary forces and assets are defined. After that the activities, which need to

be carried out for upcoming aims achieving, are planned. On this step, the activities of the defence planning and strategic employment of the Armed Forces are planned almost independently from each other.

The process of defence planning should include development planning of: defence forces and their capabilities; command and control system of defence forces; armament, military and special materiel; military infrastructure; logistics, medical, personnel and other types of support.

The important role in defence planning organization belongs to the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine and personally to the Minister. As the head of defence department, he issues the order of the Ministry of Defence, by agreement of the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, Minister of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, other heads of defence forces components concerning the principles of defence forces development planning organization, where it determines: quantitative and qualitative indicators for each component of defence forces; the procedure of defence reform joint strategic goals implementation; organization of defence forces joint training and so on. The mentioned order of the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine will allow to coordinate defence planning in all command and control bodies of the defence forces and determine the optional ways of objectives accomplishment, determined by the President of Ukraine. The results of this planning are shown in development programs of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, development programs of other military formations and law enforcement agencies (defence forces), and in the state target defence programs as well.

Therefore, the Commander-in-Chief of Ukraine should organize the formation and submission for approval to Minister of Defence of Ukraine the plans (programs) of subordinated troops (forces) by the commanders of branches and services of the Armed forces of Ukraine.

Today, the founding act in hierarchy of defence planning documents is the Military doctrine of Ukraine. In the future, such Strategy of military security should replace doctrine, as it

is practiced in Western countries. Such Strategy will be directed to achieving the determined military and political objectives. The Strategy should specialize such principles of National Security Strategy, which relate to military security sphere, determine the directions of containment and neutralization of military threats, expose the basis of defence forces development on current stage.

The Ministry of Defence of Ukraine has to be the main developer of the Military security strategy, the main tasks of which are providing of national security in the military, defence and force development spheres state policy formation and implementation in a peacetime and special period concerning the defence planning, military-technical policy in the defence sphere and military personnel policy.

We consider it appropriate to dwell on example of military enterprises development planning of our state turning to the defence planning improvement of the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine. While using development strategic planning, the defence enterprises must own key characteristics which have to include the following points:

- Flexibility, which revealed in ability to change its own management system in adaptation for new conditions of administration and regulation, increasing profitability, effectiveness and competitiveness of enterprise;

- Orientation on boosted implementation of high-tech projects, the complex programs, directed to the technical progress development in the field;

- Availability of modern management systems in process of functioning;

- Using of organizational control structures, oriented on goal achieving, and temporary groups only during the period of specific purpose directions implementation.

That's why the development of requirements for methodology of adaptation of strategic management system of defence-industrial enterprises of Ukraine, which have notable scientific and technical potential, should include the following directions:

- Detection of rivalry features in the future, in

other words, clarification the such portion of opportunities to which the defence-industrial complex enterprise of Ukraine can get the potential access regarding the leading specialization and available and possible competencies;

- Understanding of prospects and opportunities on mid-term and long-term perspective of the branch, inter-branch and internal developing for defence-industrial complex enterprise and its products competitiveness providing;

- Assessment of management skills and resource capabilities of development and execution of perspective goals and strategies of corporation developing;

- Assessment of consequences and risks while implementation of future-oriented developing strategies.

Based on all the above mentioned, the strategy of the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine enterprises development provides several key vectors:

1. Ensuring of acceptable investment environment for the involvement of western transnational corporations in Ukraine and their activity. For cooperation and competition of Ukrainian defence industry enterprises with other transnational corporation in global environment, there are good reasons to adapt Ukraine's legislation in the following spheres up to worldwide standards: intellectual property, military and technical cooperation, foreign investments in defence-industrial complex companies.

2. Neutralization of threats from the defence-industrial complex transnational corporations activity in the context of compliance economic security of our state.

3. Creation of own defence industry transnational corporations like those, which were established in the US and EU countries. The experience of these countries shows, that national capital is able to withstand competition with transnational corporations only if it is structured by its own in powerful financial-industrial groups, which will be comparable to international analogues and will be able to carry out active foreign economic policy. One of the

main directions of high effectiveness of defence-industrial complex enterprises providing should become the rational form selection of state participation in functioning of defence industry.

4. Implementation of current strategic management in the defence-industrial complex companies in parallel with appropriate efforts for functions and structures improving of national authority bodies, legal and regulatory framework of their defence-industrial complex management activity.

Besides, it is necessary to continue practice of defence inspection within the complex

supervision of security and defence sector holding, and as needed – particular defence inspections in accordance with the offered cycles of defence planning. It makes sense to widely involve non-state organizations, research institutions, as well as domestic and foreign experts, who take care of defence issues. Within the strategic communications it is useful to use mass media. Key role in the process of defence planning must be assigned to the Reform Committee of the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine and Armed Forces of Ukraine.

Conclusions

So, considering the defence planning peculiarities in the Ministry of Defence of Ukraine, and the ways of their improvement, we have the following conclusions:

- According to the Law of Ukraine “On national security of Ukraine”, the defence planning – is an integral part of state strategic planning system, which is carried out in order to provide the state defence potential by determining the priorities and directions of defence forces developing, their capabilities, armament and materiel, infrastructure, troops (forces) training, as well as development of appropriate concepts, programs and plans taking into account the real and prospective threats in military sphere and financial-economic capabilities of state;

- Positive step in Rule of Law state building with the desire to develop powerful armed forces is an existence of the proposal for legislative improvement of our state defence sphere;

- Any legislative changes should be deeply meaningful and based on achievements of already acquired experience of defence, security and military sphere issues settlement.

- While using development strategic planning, the defence enterprises must own key characteristics which have to include the following points:

a) flexibility, which revealed in ability to change its own management system in adaptation for new conditions of administration and regulation, increasing profitability, effectiveness and competitiveness of enterprise;

b) orientation on boosted implementation of high-tech projects, the complex programs, directed on the technical progress development in the field;

c) availability of modern management systems in process of functioning;

d) using of organizational control structures, oriented on goal achieving, and temporary groups only during the period of specific purpose directions implementation.

The comparative analysis of defence planning in Ukraine and Central and Eastern Europe countries, which are member-states of NATO, should be specified among the perspective research directions of this topic.

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